

EVALUATION OF MICROBIOLOGICAL AND PHYSICO-CHEMICAL QUALITY PROPERTIES OF HORSE MEAT SAUSAGE ‘CHUCHUK’

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ABSTRACT. The consumption of horsemeat is a traditional practice in several Asian countries, including Kyrgyzstan. This study aimed to evaluate chuchuk samples made from horse meat regarding their physicochemical and microbiological quality properties. For that purpose, 32 samples of chuchuk samples from bazars in the Chuy region of Kyrgyzstan were collected aseptically and under cold chain conditions, then subjected to microbiological and physicochemical analyses. The results of the microbiological quality assessment for horsemeat chuchuk revealed mean and maximum values expressed as log₁₀ CFU/g. The findings for mean and maximum values were as follows: total aerobic mesophilic bacteria (7.54; 8.91), total psychrophilic microorganisms (7.34; 8.97), enterobacter (2.46; 7.76), coliform (1.96; 7.84), *E. coli* (0.31; 4.55), *Enterococcus* (4.94; 6.67), *S. aureus* (5.89; 7.73), *Pseudomonas* spp. (1.22; 6.64), *Clostridium* spp. (0.12; 2.70), lactic acid bacteria (7.58; 9.02), and yeast/mold (6.17; 8.67). Also, mean values for physicochemical parameters are as follows: pH (6.32), dry matter (33.04), ash (2.37), protein (19.78), fat (31.82), water activity (aw) (0.96). Results indicated increased levels of TAM, pathogens, and indicator microbes. This highlights the potential health risks associated with non-standardized and primitive production conditions and the lack of compliance with hygiene standards throughout the production and storage of chuchuk in the surveyed units. Likewise, standardized production methods and basic hygiene measures are essential to ensure that chuchuk are safe to eat and regulatory authorities need to be consistent in carrying out hygiene inspections and in enforcing dissuasive measures against non-compliant establishments. In addition, the implementation of Good Manufacturing Practices (GMP) and Hazard Analysis and Critical Control Points (HACCP) can constitute useful tools in covering the food chain from production to consumption, in line with the concept of 'food safety from farm to fork'.

Keywords: *Chuchuk, horse meat, microbiological analysis, physico-chemical properties, food hygiene.*

INTRODUCTION

Meat is a significant part of a balanced and healthy diet and has played a key role in human evolution [1]. Humans have been eating wild horse meat as early as the Paleolithic era [2]. Evidence suggests that horses were employed as a food source for humans before their domestication. The domestication of horses can be traced back to the end of the Neolithic period (6000-5000 B.C.) by the nomadic societies of Central Asia. The discovery of horse bones in archaeological excavations and cave paintings dating back to the Paleolithic period (10.000 B.C.), also indicates that horses were hunted for food in Western Europe [3]. Horse meat and its products are considered high-nutritional-value foods [4]. Horse meat is low in cholesterol and fat and contains a high amount of iron [5]. Horsemeat is characterized by a high protein content with significant biological value, coupled with a low-fat content with a desirable fatty acid profile. The preservation process makes the cured horsemeat a product with an extended shelf life, which makes it attractive both as a food product for consumption and as a raw material for further processing [2]. Available research data highlighted that horse meat is traditionally used in many countries such as Morocco, France, Italy, Mexico, Japan, Kyrgyzstan, Kazakhstan, China, Mongolia, Iceland, Switzerland, Croatia, Belgium, Russia, Finland, Malta, Ukraine, and Greece, respectively [3, 5–8]. Its consumption is increasing in some Western European countries [3]. Additionally, horse meat is used to make sucuk (a type of dry sausage), a meat derived product obtained by using certain spices, smoking, fermentation, or cooking methods [9]. Horse meat and mare's milk have been traditionally used in Kyrgyz cuisine since ancient times. Horse meat is known as "kazi karta" in the Kyrgyz language and is usually served as a cold appetizer. The part of the horse meat used in sucuk making, which consists of rib fat and meat, is called "kazi." [10, 11]. Sucuk made from rib meat is considered the most valuable product of the horse [12]. Sausage made from horse meat is referred to as "chuchuk." [11, 13]. According to published data by the global horse meat market, the horse meat production constitutes less than 0.25% of the total world meat production, with a total of 700,000 tons of this type of meat per year. Moreover, in Europe, recent concerns such as dioxin contamination, foot-and-mouth disease, and bovine encephalopathy have been encountered in farm animals. As a result, consumers have begun to seek alternative red meats from non-traditional species. In this context, the increasing importance of horse meat is gaining more attention [1, 14].

The objective of the present study was to evaluate of the physico-chemical and microbiological quality of horsemeat sausage, specifically 'chuchuk', sold to the consumer in the bazaars of the Chuy region of Kyrgyzstan.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Materials

A total of 32 samples of chuchuk, a traditional horse meat derived product, available in the bazaars of the Chuy region of Kyrgyzstan were used as material in this study. The samples were randomly collected from the sales locations and transferred to the laboratory in sterile glass jars of at least 100 grams each, under aseptic conditions and in a cold chain at +4 °C, and immediately subjected to microbiological and physico-chemical analyses.

Microbiological analyses

The collected samples were divided into small pieces. Then, 10 grams of each sample was taken and mixed with 90 ml of physiological saline solution using a stomacher for 3 minutes. Next, 1 ml of the mixture was taken with a sterile pipette and decimal dilutions to 10^9 were made. Microbiological analyses were conducted by inoculating appropriate culture media with the prepared dilutions, following the methods described by Kurt et al. [15] and Harrigan [16]. The culture media, incubation conditions, and inoculation methods used to analyze the samples are listed in Table 1.

Table 1. Culture media, incubation conditions, and inoculation methods used during microbiological analysis of the present study.

Targeted microorganism	Culture medium	Inoculation method	Incubation (aerobic)	Reference
TAM	Plate Count Agar (LABM LAB149)	Pour plate	30 °C 72 hours	[17, 18]
TPM	Plate Count Agar (LABM LAB149)	Pour plate	4±1 °C 10 days	[18, 19]
Enterobacter	Violet Red Bile Glucose Agar (LABM LAB088)	Pour plate	30 °C 24 hours	[18, 20]
Coliform	Violet Red Bile Lactose Agar (LABM LAB031)	Pour plate	37 °C 24 hours	[21, 22]
<i>E. coli</i>	Tryptone Bile Glucuronide Agar (LABM HAL003)	Spread plate	30 °C 4 hours and 44 °C 18 hours	[18, 23]
Enterococcus	Slanetz&Bartley Medium (LABM LAB166)	Spread plate	37 °C 4 hours and 44 °C 24-48 hours	[18]
<i>S. aureus</i>	Baird-Parker Agar (Oxoid CM275)	Spread plate	37 °C 24-48 hours	[22, 24]
<i>Pseudomonas</i> spp.	Pseudomonas Agar and CFC Supplement (Oxoid CM559+SR103)	Spread plate	25±1 °C 24-48 hours	[22, 25]
<i>Clostridium</i> spp.	Sulfit Polymyxin Sulfadiazine Agar (Merck 1.10235)	Roll tube	37 °C 24 hours	[26, 27]
Lactic Acid Bacteria	De Man, Rogasa) Agar (Oxoid CM361)	Pour plate	37±1 °C 24-48 hours	[22, 27]
Yeast mold	Potato Dextrose Agar (LABM LAB098)	Pour plate	20-25 °C 5 days	[18, 28]

TAM: Total mesophilic aerobic microorganisms, TPM: Total psychrophilic microorganisms

Chemical Analyses

The pH values of the horse chuchuk samples were determined by a pH meter (Hanna® PH 890, UK) [29]. Briefly, samples were dried in an oven at 105°C to determine the dry matter content (Nüve, EN550, Turkey) as were previously described by [30]. The ash content was measured in an ash furnace (Thermo Scientific, K114, USA) following the working methodology described by [31]. The protein content was determined using a Kjeldahl apparatus (KJELDATHERM®, Gerhardt, Germany) as indicated by [32]. The fat content was determined using the specified method in American Oil Chemists Society (AOCS) [33]. The water activity values were measured using an aw meter (Novasina® MS 1 Set, Switzerland) [34].

Statistical Analysis

The statistical analysis of the obtained results was done using the SPSS (Version 13) statistical software package. Pearson correlation analysis was employed to determine the significance level of the relationship between variables (SPSS, 2006).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results of microbiological and chemical analysis of the processing of the 32 chuchuk samples, including the recorded overall average value of the each targeted microorganisms are summary presented in Table 2 and Table 3, respectively.

Table 2. Microbiological analysis results (expressed as log₁₀ CFU/g) determined in horse chuchuk samples.

Targeted microorganism	Mean Value	Minimum	Maximum
TAM	7.54 ± 0.14	5.60	8.91
TPM	7.34 ± 0.20	3.01	8.97
Enterobacter	2.46 ± 0.36	n.d.	7.76
Coliform	1.96 ± 0.35	n.d.	7.84
<i>E. coli</i>	0.31 ± 0.18	n.d.	4.55
Enterococcus	4.94 ± 0.24	n.d.	6.67
<i>S. aureus</i>	5.89 ± 0.35	n.d.	7.73
<i>Pseudomonas</i> spp.	1.22 ± 0.39	n.d.	6.64
<i>Clostridium</i> spp.	0.12 ± 0.09	n.d.	2.70
Lactic Acid Bacteria	7.58 ± 0.14	5.41	9.02
Yeast mold	6.17 ± 0.22	3.09	8.67

Mean ± standard error; n = 32, n.d.: not detected.

Microbiological criteria provide targets and reference points to assist competent authorities and food businesses operators in managing and monitoring the safety of the finished products, although microbiological testing alone does not guarantee the safety of a tested food matrices [35]. In present investigation in the examined samples, the average count of TAM was determined to be 7.54±0.14 log cfu/g ranging from 5.60 to 8.91 log cfu/g. In another study conducted by Bocholoev et al. [36] found TAM counts of 2.00±1.55, 3.83±0.2, and 5.28±0.65 in their research, which are lower than the values obtained in the present investigation. The high microbial load in the samples indicates

contamination of products sold in open markets in the screened region. In horse sausage samples, the average count of total aerobic psychrophilic microorganisms was determined as 7.34 ± 0.20 log cfu/g in the present study. Bocholoev et al. [36] reported TPM counts ranging from 0 to 6.37 ± 0.14 . Our results are consistent with this study. Members of the *Enterobacteriaceae* family are among the most encountered microorganisms in food. This family includes coliform groups such as *Escherichia*, *Enterobacter*, *Klebsiella*, and *Citrobacter*, as well as various genera containing pathogenic species isolated mostly from animal intestines, such as *Shigella* spp., *Salmonella* spp., *Morganella* spp., *Providencia* spp., *Edwardsiella* spp., *Proteus* spp., *Yersinia* spp., and *Serratia* spp. [37]. They are generally used as indicator microorganisms to assess the inadequate hygiene, processing, or post-processing contamination of food [38]. Their absence ensures the proper hygiene and implementation of food production processes, while their presence often indicates a potential problem or failure during the production process [39, 40]. In our study, *Enterobacter*, *Enterococcus*, coliform bacteria and *E. coli* were evaluated as indicators of fecal contamination. These bacteria were not present in some samples but were detected in others. The average count of enterobacteria in the analyzed sausage samples was 2.46 ± 0.36 log cfu/g, reaching a maximum value of 7.76 cfu/g. Additionally, the average count of coliform bacteria in the horse sausage samples was found to be 1.96 ± 0.35 log cfu/g, with a maximum value of 7.84 cfu/g (Table 2). The average count of *E. coli* in the examined sausages was ranged from not determined (n.d.) to 4.55 cfu/g with an average of 0.31 ± 0.18 log cfu/g. Moreover, the *Enterococcus* count in the present study was determined to be 4.94 ± 0.24 log cfu/g and the highest value of *Enterococcus* was 6.67 cfu/g. In another study, Boçoloev et al. [36] reported that in two regions of Kyrgyzstan they did not encounter *enterobacteria* but found counts of 3.67 ± 0.17 cfu/g in one region. Although *S. aureus* was not detected in some of the examined horse sausage samples, the maximum value for this bacteria was found to be as 7.73 cfu/g in this study. In a study conducted in Algeria, Hachemi et al. [41] reported that the sausage samples had a *S. aureus* count of 5.26 ± 0.45 cfu/g. In another investigation conducted in Morocco, Ed-Dra et al. [42] found the presence of *S. aureus* in 63 (40.38%) out of 156 sausage samples. The presence of *Pseudomonas* spp. was observed in some samples, and the average value for this bacteria 1.22 ± 0.39 cfu/g. The average for *Clostridium* spp. was 0.12 ± 0.09 cfu/g. Lactic acid bacteria level was ranged from 5.41 cfu/g to 9.02 cfu/g, while yeast/mold level was 6.17 ± 0.22 cfu/g. In an experimental study, the lactic acid bacteria count was ranged from 7.15 cfu/g to 7.59 cfu/g and yeast/mould was ranged from 4.05 cfu/g to 4.35 cfu/g [43]. Statistical analysis of the analyzed sausage samples revealed a significant positive relationship between TAM and *S. aureus* ($p < 0.05$), lactobacillus count, and pH ($p < 0.01$). A positive relationship between TPM and *enterococcus* count ($p < 0.01$), as well as lactobacillus count ($p < 0.05$) were also observed. In the study, a positive important relationship was seen between *enterobacter* and coliform group microorganisms ($p < 0.01$), *E. coli*, *Enterococcus*, *Pseudomonas* spp., and yeast-mold ($p < 0.05$). In addition, a positive significant relationship was observed between coliform group microorganisms and *Pseudomonas* spp. ($p < 0.05$); A positive significant relationship was observed between *enterococcus* and *S. aureus* and lactobacillus bacteria ($p < 0.05$). A negative relationship was observed between *Enterococcus*.

Table 3. Physical and chemical analysis results of sucuk samples.

Parameter	Mean	Minimum	Maximum
pH	6.32 ± 0,05	6.05	7.27
Dry matter	33.04 ± 2.42	11.7	91.07
Ash	2.37 ± 0.18	0.5	5.69
Protein	19.78 ± 0.89	9.28	31.61
Fat	31.82 ± 2.27	10.32	65.91
aw	0.96 ± 0.00	0.91	1.00

Mean ± standard error; n = 32

The average pH value detected in the samples was determined to be 6.32±0.05. This number was found to be similar to the values reported by in another study [36]. The average dry matter content detected in the samples was determined to be 33.04±2.42%. This value was lower than reported by another study [36]. The differences between the studies are thought to be due to variations in the drying times, drying environments, and temperature. The average ash content detected in the samples was determined to be 2.37±0.18%. This value was lower than the values determined by Bocholoev et al. [36]. The different values between these two studies can be attributed to the use of additives like salt and spices during the production period. The average aw value was determined as 0.96±0.00. The average of protein was detected in the samples as 19.78±0.89%. Also, the fat content was determined as 31.82±2.27%. Another study also evaluated the protein and fat levels of horse meat sausage. They reported protein values between 16.18±0.16 and 37.83±0.2, while the fat content was reported as 31.86±0.20 [36]. The variation between the studies can be caused by differences between the fat and meat amounts which were incorporated into the product. Individual taste preferences and the different meat/fat ratios of different producers may affect this. Also, differences between studies can be attributed to the lack of a standardized approach during sausage production and subjectivity in determining meat and fat proportions.

CONCLUSION

The results of the study emphasized that levels of TAM, pathogens and indicator micro-organisms were found relatively high. These results indicated that hygiene standards are not being adequately maintained at all stages of the production and storage of chuchuk sausage. The recorded high levels of the monitored microorganisms indicate the lack of standardization in the production of chuchuk and the potential health risks associated with production under primitive conditions. To ensure the safe presentation of chuchuk to consumers, the necessary hygiene measures must be taken, in particular by establishing standardized production for this product. The production of this product, which is currently being made in small family settings, should be shifted to modern facilities. Displaying and selling products in the open air under bazaar conditions can lead to contamination by undesirable microorganisms, posing a risk to public health. Also, this concern can be exacerbated by the conditions in the bazaar where the cold chain is broken. Regulatory authorities should conduct hygiene inspections in accordance with the regulations without interruption, and deterrent sanctions should be implemented for non-compliant establishments. The implementation of Good Manufacturing Practices (GMP) and Hazard Analysis and Critical Control Points (HACCP) throughout the entire chain

from production to consumption should be ensured to comply with the "farm-to-table food safety" concept. Also, to ensure optimal preservation and quality, it is recommended that chuchuk are sold to consumers in vacuum-sealed packaging and maintained within the cold chain until they reach the consumer.

Conflict of Interest. The authors declared that there is no conflict of interest.

Authorship Contributions. Concept: F.R.I., R.M.T., Design: F.R.I., R.M.T., U.A., Data Collection or Processing: F.R.I., R.M.T., Analysis or Interpretation: F.R.I., R.M.T., D.A-A, Y.C.S, Literature Search: F.R.I., R.M.T., D.A-A, Y.C.S, U.A., Writing: F.R.I., R.M.T., D.A-A, Y.C.S, U.A.

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